

INTELLIGENT MANUFACTURING DURING THE RESIN TRANSFER MOLDING PROCESS TO INCREASE YIELD

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1. Abstract

The Resin Transfer Molding (RTM) process, in which the preform is placed in a closed mold and resin is impregnated to cover all the empty spaces between the fibers, has been used to manufacture high-performance polymer composite parts, however prototype development costs and unpredictable results have prevented many from exploring its possibilities. Lack of understanding of the resin flow behavior results in regions of fibers with resin (dry spots) and the composite part is rejected. Parameters are “guessed” based on the results from the rejected part and experience to attempt the next trial. If process models and simulations are used in an effective way, science could replace the guesswork and improve the manufacturing process despite the presence of variability in the process. This paper demonstrates how computer simulations and design can be used to understand the process and control the fluid flow to avoid dry spots in a framework of a workstation which can be used to manufacture a multitude of prototypes. First, it will be demonstrated why and how the resin impregnation process is not repeatable even under the same processing condition with the same materials in an identical environment. Next, examples of how passive and active flow control strategies can be used to design gate and vent locations and their actuation to produce a part despite the presence of variability during the manufacturing. Finally, a RTM workstation that can execute the strategies developed in an automated way by incorporating the concept of modular molding as well as a new injection approach is discussed.

KEY WORDS: Resin Transfer Molding, Control, Automation, Numerical Simulation, Modular Molding, Gate and Vent Locations, Composites Manufacturing, Liquid Composite Molding, Passive Control, Active Control, Flow Sensors

2. Introduction

The Resin Transfer Molding (RTM) process is used to manufacture net shape composite parts. It is especially beneficial when high fiber volume fractions, complex part geometries, and tight dimensional tolerances are desired. The steps of this process, shown in Figure 1, are as follows: In this process, a mold is prepared, and the pre-cut fibers are placed into the mold. The mold is then closed and sealed using a press or perimeter bolting. Then, a thermoset liquid polymer resin is injected into the mold through gates, and the air entrapped in the mold during closure is displaced and escapes through vents. Once the injection is complete, the resin is allowed to cure and harden. Once the curing is complete, the mold is opened and the part is removed and inspected for quality assurance.

Figure 1: The various stages of the Resin Transfer Molding process

Removed parts are considered unacceptable if certain areas are void of any resin and contain only fiber. These regions will not have the structural support necessary. These resin-void areas, or dry spots, as seen in Figure 2, are created when the air entrapped by the closing process has not properly escaped through the vents.

Figure 2: Parts containing dry spots, or areas of dry fabric, result in poor mechanical performance and must be discarded

Therefore, there is an important, and often misunderstood relationship between the location of gates and vents and the location (if any) of dry spots. This process of gate and vent location has historically relied on personal experience and trial and error guesswork as one cannot visualize the impregnation process once the mold is closed.

3. Simulation of LCM Processes

To gain a better understanding of the filling stage of the RTM process, the process can be mathematically modeled and a computer simulation [1][2] can allow one to “visualize” inside a closed mold. Such a program can predict the flow behavior and therefore help to intelligently decide upon the gate and vent placement. With this goal in mind, a program, Liquid Injection Molding Simulation (LIMS) [3][4] was

developed at the University of Delaware. LIMS is a finite element – control volume solver. It was designed to be a fast solver, utilizing various algorithms to reduce the computational time.

Figure 3: With the input of geometry, material data, and proper mathematical modeling, LIMS can simulate the filling stage of LCM processes

It is also a very flexible program which allows it to be used to explore very complex injection schemes. It allows the user to select gate locations and then to see the resulting flow patterns to determine the success of the filling. It also allows triggering of any gates to be closed or opened during the filling process based upon any condition such as time, resin arrival at a certain location, etc. This allows one to simulate such scenarios as sequential injection or implement complicated control strategies. Access to all of the state variables during the simulation allows one to learn a great deal about the process.

3.1. Need for Material Data

In order to have an accurate simulation, the material data that is provided must be accurate. For the filling stage of Liquid Composite Molding processes, the important parameters are the mold geometry, the resin viscosity, and the properties of the fiber preform. These include the fiber volume fraction and the permeability. It is this last property that is the most critical, and usually the most difficult to obtain. The permeability describes the resistance that the fiber poses to the flowing fluid. It is a tensor quantity that relates the fluid pressure gradients to the flow velocities. The physics of the process are described by Darcy’s Law, which is written as:

$$\vec{u} = -\frac{1}{\eta} [k] \nabla P$$

The permeability [5] can be analytically or numerically estimated, but the most reliable method for determining the permeability is through experimentation. Various experimental techniques can be used to obtain the preform permeability [6][7].

3.2. Variations in data

One of the difficulties in obtaining preform permeability is due to the inherent variability in the data. From location to location within a roll of fabric, the permeability can vary. However, the largest variability in the progression of resin through the preform is due to difficulty of repeating the process of fiber placement in the mold. The non-reproducible factors that contribute to this are (i) fabric cutting to fit the mold cavity exactly, (ii) stacking and nesting of the fiber layers in the mold (iii) fiber density and volume fraction along the edges of the mold cavity. This will create a slight air channel in the space between the mold edge and the fabric.

Figure 4: Race tracking is caused by an imperfect fit between the fabric and mold, resulting in faster flow.

This air gap, or race tracking channel [8], shown in Figure 4, will create an area that will pose little resistance to the flowing fluid. This race tracking channel can cause the fluid to flow faster in these region, and therefore result in a flow pattern different from expected. This effect of race tracking is nearly unavoidable and difficult to characterize. Due to the non-precise nature of the lay-up process, the amount of the race tracking can vary from one part to the next.

Figure 5: (a) The geometry and race tracking edges for the study and (b) experimental setup

An experimental case study was conducted in an L shaped mold shown in Figure 5, where race tracking was expected along the five edges shown in the figure. Experiments were done by different users, each conducting ten experiments. Measurements of race tracking strength in the 50 experiments conducted shown in Figure 6 and confirms the non-repeatability of the strength of race tracking along these edges.

Figure 6: The race tracking strengths shown by edge and by user.

Figure 7: The standard deviation of the data shown by edge and by user.

4. Need for Control

As can be seen from the studies above, there is a great variability in the relative permeability values from experiment to experiment. This will result in differing flow patterns from one part to the next, which may result in the last region to be filled to differ. With fixed locations of gates and vents, certain scenarios may not be filled properly. This could result in a certain percentage of parts to be discarded due to dry spots. For this reason, it is necessary to use control [9][10][11] of the filling stage to increase the yield of successful injections so that wastage is decreased. There are various methods and techniques for applying control to the filling state of LCM processes, and the following sections will describe two main categories: passive and active control.

5. Passive Control

One approach to increase the yield of successful parts is passive control of the filling process. In order to have a completely impregnated fiber preform, vents must be located at the last locations to be filled so that all of the air is able to escape. Therefore, more the number of vents that are located throughout the mold, more likely it is the filling will displace the air completely. However, additional vents are expensive, as they require setup and cleanup, extra machining, and can result in surface imperfections in the finished part. Therefore, there is a balance in having more vents to properly remove all of the air and fewer vents to facilitate the manufacturing. The aim of passive control is to intelligently select gate and vent combinations that will properly fill the part for the most number of scenarios. In order to accomplish

this, it is necessary to first identify the location where the permeability may deviate from the anticipated. These are primarily edges, where race tracking is likely to occur. Then, it is necessary to identify the likelihood of various levels of race tracking to occur at each location. Since this is most naturally expressed as a probability, probabilistic mapping lends itself to this problem. In the following, we present an example of a passive control study to demonstrate the methodology and the benefit.

The details of this study can be found in [12]. To demonstrate the concept of vent selection for passive control, the geometry shown in Figure 8 was selected. Five identified race tracking edges were the top, bottom, and right edges, as well as the two perimeters of the inserts.

Figure 8: Schematic of geometry and race tracking channels for passive control example

Four distinct levels of race tracking were selected, and appropriate probabilities for each of those levels occurring along each edge were assigned, as summarized in Figure 8. This will result in 1024 scenarios in which every permutation of race tracking along the five edges is considered. Mold filling simulations were performed for these 1024 scenarios and the regions to fill last were recorded in every scenario. Probability associated with each race tracking edge was used to create a vent map. The details can be found in [12]. After the process of vent optimization was performed, the resulting vents as seen in Figure 9 were found for three vents solution. As a reference, a set of vents based upon intuition were selected. With the intuitive vents selected, a success rate of 28% was obtained. When the combinatorial search was utilized, the resultant vents resulted in a 69% success rate. This demonstrates how by simply placing vents in the ideal location as opposed to random placement, the success rate of manufacturing can increase drastically. A part was considered to be successfully filled if the void content was less than 1%.

Figure 9: Comparison of vent placement based on intuition and using combinatorial search (cs) method based on simulations. The intuitive method resulted in only 28% success rate where as cs improved it to 69%

6. Active Control

No combination of gates and vents can guarantee that 100% of the injections will result in complete filled parts. Additionally, certain geometries may require an excessive number of vents to ensure that a sufficient percentage of successful parts are manufactured. Additionally, the methodology may require one to place the vents in locations that are not allowed by the tooling used. If any of these situations occur, it may be necessary to use active control. In active control, auxiliary injection gates are placed and can be used in different combinations to manipulate the flow front to drive the fluid towards the vents. It is possible to have control over when individual gates may be opened or closed, as well as the pressure or flow rate that will be injected through it. Again, off-line simulations can be used to determine the likely scenarios to occur and the likely control actions that can help avoid creation of the dry spot. Thus such simulations can provide ideal auxiliary gate locations as well as their timing sequences and gate conditions. Next, we present an example to demonstrate the methodology pursued in active control of mold filling. The details of this study can be found in [13]. The first step in generating a control study is to select a geometry and to identify the potential regions of disturbance. Figure 10 shows the geometry selected for this study and identifies the edges for potential race tracking to occur.

Figure 10: Selected geometry with 5 regions for race tracking, along with locations of vent, flow detection sensors, and auxiliary gates

Initially, the left and right edges are used to inject via a line injection. The flow will develop and race tracking will occur at some level along the top and bottom edges, as well as the edges around the triangular insert. With all of these scenarios generated and the flow patterns predicted, a simulation called SLIC was developed to analyze the data from these scenarios to find the optimal sensor locations that will allow the system to best differentiate between the various scenarios. The fluid arrival time at each sensor for each scenario in the simulation is recorded into a file for later comparison with the actual experimental arrival times to identify the scenario in real time. Once the scenario is identified, one must have a customized control action for that scenario to redirect the flow in such a way as to avoid a dry spot. SLIC is used again off-line to design the customized control action for each scenario that can be invoked in real time once the scenario is identified. SLIC uses genetic algorithms to place auxiliary gates and flow control trigger sensors to open and close these auxiliary gates when the resin reaches the flow control trigger sensors for every scenario generated. The customized control actions are stored in a file to be invoked during the real experiment once the scenario is identified. For this case study, the sensors and auxiliary gates are placed as shown in Figure 10. Once all of the off-line design work is done, the results can be confirmed through experimentation. A mold was prepared to validate these results, and the experimental apparatus is shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Experimental setup to validate the simulated results

Several experiments were run to validate the control methodology and test the success rate of the control actions for various scenarios. For each case, the experiment was initiated, the sensors identified the scenario that was taking place, and finally the auxiliary control gates were initiated at the appropriate time. Finally, the flow was allowed to continue until the mold was completely filled. An example of the flow progression as seen during the experiment and predicted by the simulation is shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Resulting flow fronts from (a) experiment and (b) predicted simulation during a control experiment

Several experiments were conducted in the same manner, and in each case, despite different scenarios occurring, the mold was completely filled due to the control actions taken. From this study, it can be seen how active control can be used to ensure a complete filling without introducing a large number of gates and vents despite the presence of non-repeatable race tracking along the edges.

7. Motivation for RTM Station

The above work demonstrates how it is necessary to use simulations, sensors and active control to increase the yield of the process in which the disturbances are non-repeatable. It is necessary to consider the design of the control system before the mold itself is designed, because the ideal location of gates and vents may not coincide with the most obvious location from a molding standpoint. Once a mold is made, it can be very difficult to add additional vents or gates to satisfy a control strategy. Of larger concern, for each new part geometry to be created is that an entire new mold must be fabricated. It could benefit composite part prototyping and research efforts in RTM if an easier molding approach could be pursued.

7.3. Modular Molding

The basic components of the workstation are a fixed set of top and bottom plates, which one could raise or lower with a hydraulic system to open and close the mold. The surfaces of the press plates would be the actual molding surfaces for the mold.

Figure 13: Modular molding (left) allows one to create different parts with a minimum of new mold components by means of an injection network (right)

When new part geometry is desired, it would only be necessary to design and manufacture a mold frame and necessary inserts. This would reduce the number of mold components needed for each part geometry as demonstrated in Figure 13. This could easily allow one to switch from making tapered parts to making ribbed parts, or other net shape geometries. Additionally, all mold hardware would be reusable and in place for operation. The injection machinery and all associated components would be a permanent fixture on the RTM Workstation.

7.4. New Injection Approach

An array of controllable gates and vents are dispersed over the surface of the platens. This allows a user a great flexibility in injection design. Typical injection and venting requires the use of plastic tubing to bring the resin from the injection machine to the mold. With such an array of gates and vents, an excessive amount of such tubing would be required. For this reason, a new injection approach will be employed here. A channel based resin delivery system is the starting point of this injection approach. The channels, seen in Figure 13 will interconnect the entire gate network, and tie it to a common central source location. Therefore, only one piece of tubing would be necessary to deliver the resin to the mold, and then the channels would distribute the resin throughout the mold. In order to gain individual control over each gate, a piston / plunger system is to be placed below each injection location. When the piston is lowered, the fluid will pass through the injection hole and into the mold cavity. With the piston raised, the plunger will be pressed against the plate and block the fluid from entering the mold cavity. In addition, mold-imbedded flush sensors [14][15][16] will be installed to aid in flow detection.

Figure 14: The new injection approach gives individual control to an array of gates

To prevent the curing resin from destroying the piston, a flexible membrane is placed between the two plates. In addition to protecting the pistons, the membrane will also provide a better seal between the plunger and the upper plate. The entire system is shown in Figure 14.

7.5. Applications for further study

This RTM Workstation will allow one to easily explore manufacturing new components from composite materials in a low production level with little additional cost or time. The array of gates is always available and requires no configuring. It is merely necessary to make a new spacer plate and any inserts that may be needed. Furthermore, this RTM Workstation allows researchers to continue to investigate different flow control strategies to validate simulated work.

8. Conclusion

The discussions above outlined two areas of significant cost wastage in the Resin Transfer Molding process. One is due to the wastage of materials and time due to discarding improperly impregnated parts. This issue can be addressed through either using passive or active control, or a combination of the two. Several experimental examples were given to outline and explain these concepts. The other area of significant cost is molding for low production processing. If a modular methodology is used, the major mold components can be used for a family of net shaped geometries. This can reduce the number of specific mold components for each new geometry. A new injection approach incorporates these two concerns and creates a test bed for the RTM process to aid in prototyping and research efforts alike.

9. Acknowledgments

The authors gratefully acknowledge the support provided by the Office of Naval Research (ONR) under Grant #N00014-97-C-0415 for the "Advanced Materials Intelligent Processing Center" at the University of Delaware.

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